

TOUGHENING OF SiC/LAS III CERAMIC COMPOSITES BY 3-D HYBRID FIBER ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

Previous study indicated that the room temperature out-of-plane properties of SiC/LAS III composites can be dramatically improved by 3-D braided fiber architecture. After ceraming, the properties of the composites were reduced by an order of magnitude due to strength degradation of the Nicalon SiC fibers at temperatures above 600°C. In order to preserve the composite strength after processing and enhance the high temperature properties of the composites, SCS-6 SiC filaments which have a significantly higher thermal stability than Nicalon SiC, were introduced into a 3-D network of Nicalon β -SiC to produce a hybrid fiber structure. The in-plane and out-of-plane properties of the hybrid composites were characterized along with microstructural analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for high temperature materials has brought increased attention to the field of ceramic matrix composites. Taking advantage of the high temperature resistance of ceramic materials and the toughening properties of fibrous reinforcement, these advanced materials are being introduced into high temperature structural applications such as advanced turbine engine components.

In order to achieve enhanced toughness for ceramics, the matrix is reinforced by short fibers or filament wound systems in laminate form. The delamination potential of these material systems results in relatively low transverse and shear stresses and possible catastrophic failure. To improve the interlaminar strength and reduce the potential for brittle failure, the concept of structural toughening of ceramic matrix composites by 3-D fiber architecture was demonstrated using Nicalon SiC in LAS glass matrix[1]. It was found, as shown in Figure 1, the flexural strength of the 3-D braided composites compare favorably to the 12 harness satin weave laminates and through stitched laminates .

In order to facilitate high temperature processing and expand the concept of structural toughening to temperature regimes beyond the capability of Nicalon fibers, multiphase SiC filaments such as Avco's SCS SiC were considered. Due to the large diameter inherent to the SiC filaments it is difficult if not impossible to process these fibers into integrated structures. It was felt that a combination of the thermally stable Avco SCS monofilaments with the more processable Nicalon SiC fibers in a 3-D fiber network would produce a composite system which has a well balanced in-plane and out-of-plane properties.

Accordingly, it is the objective of this study to investigate the effects of hybridizing Nicalon[®] β -SiC yarn with Avco SCS-6 monofilament CVD SiC filaments. The hybrid preforms were fabricated with various proportions of longitudinal SCS filaments inserted in a 3-D braided network of Nicalon yarns and consolidated with an LAS III (Lithium Alumina Silicate) glass ceramic by slurry infiltration. The properties of the hybrid composites were characterized by simple tensile, four point flex, and through thickness tensile test along with fractography.

THE MATERIALS SYSTEM

The two candidate SiC fibers selected for this study are the SCS-6 filament from Avco and the Nicalon multifilament yarns produced by Nippon Carbon. A summary of the properties provided by the fiber producers is given in Table I.

Table I. Properties of Silicon Carbide Fibers

Properties	SCS-6	Nicalon
Fiber Diameter (μm)	140	14
Density (g/cc)	3.045	2.55
Tensile Strength (MPa)	3400	2000
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	414	104
CTE ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$)	3.6	3.1

As shown in Figure 2, the Avco SCS-6[®] SiC monofilament formed by CVD on a carbon substrate filament, has good strength retention up to 1,000°C in a non-oxidizing environment and up to 700°C in an oxidizing environment. However, as this monofilament is formed by CVD process, the resulting filament diameter is 140 μm , which makes this material unwieldy for textile applications.

The second SiC component of the hybrid composite is Nicalon[®] which has an average filament diameter of 14 μm and is consequently much more suitable for textile processes. However, as illustrated in Figure 3, the strength after thermal exposure for the Nicalon fiber is considerably lower than that of the SCS filaments. In both oxidizing and argon environments, the Nicalon yarn shows a strength loss of more than an order of magnitude after exposure to a temperature above 600°C. This loss of strength can be attributed to the chemical composition of Nicalon which is manufactured by the pyrolysis of melt-spun polycarbosilane. It is believed that the presence of free carbon and oxidation of SiC is a primary cause for thermal degradation. Table II illustrates the chemical composition of the SiC fibers.

Table II. Chemical Composition of SiC Fibers

Composition (wt%)	Nicalon	SCS-6
Si	55.5	70
C	28.4	30
O	14.9	trace
H	0.13	----
Molecular Composition (wt%)		
SiC	61	99+
SiO ₂	28	----
Free C	10	trace
Free Si	trace	----

Although the thermo-mechanical properties of Nicalon SiC fibers may not be adequate for very high temperature applications, the Nicalon fiber is perhaps the most suitable commercially available model fiber for the demonstration of the hybrid concept because of the availability of a good data base coupled with the fiber's textile processability.

THE PROCESSING OF THE HYBRID COMPOSITE SYSTEM

To develop this hybrid reinforcement concept, 3-D braided Nicalon yarns were combined with various proportions of the SCS lay-in SiC filaments. As detailed in a review article by Ko [2], 3-D braiding is an extension of the well established 2-D braiding technology which intertwines three or more systems of yarns in an orthogonal manner. The fibers in the resulting structure are oriented in the off-axis as well as through-thickness direction. Intimately entwined with the braided structure were the Avco SCS-6 filaments, introduced as axial lay-in systems. Various ratios of braiding yarn(Nicalon) and longitudinal lay-in yarns(SCS-6) were used ranging from 100/0 to 75/25, 50/50 and 25/75 (e.g. %Nicalon fiber/%Avco filament). The orientation of the surface braiding yarns ranges from +/- (10 to 20) degrees . Fabrication of the composites was carried out by a slurry infiltration technique followed by a vacuum hot pressing consolidation. The composites had a nominal fiber volume fraction of 40%. Figure 4a and 4b illustrate a typical cross-sectional micrograph of a consolidated 100/0 and 50/50 Nicalon/SCS composite respectively. In Fig.4a the intertwining pattern of braiding yarns are clearly shown for the 100% braided composite. Fig.4b shows that the distribution of the large SCS-6 filaments surrounded by the Nicalon yarns into clustered filament bundles.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Simple tensile, four point flexural and through thickness tensile tests were performed on the hybrid composites. Because of the limited availability of the specimens for testing, the variables of scatter associated with these brittle materials could not be evaluated. After testing, scanning electron micrography was performed on the specimens to characterize modes of failure. Table II provides a summary of the flexure, tensile and through thickness properties of the composites.

Table II. Mechanical Properties of Hybrid SiC/LAS III Glass Matrix Composites

Ratio of Braiding Yarn to Longitudinal Filament (%Nicalon/%Avco SCS-6)

Property	100/0	75/25	50/50	25/75
Fiber Volume Fraction	.4	.38	.4	.4
Fiber Orientation (degrees)	16	14	12	20
Tensile Strength (MPa)	393	656	>535*	>621*
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	92	166	168	300
Flexural Strength (MPa)	359	311	218	228
Flexural Modulus (GPa)	114	124	97	112
Through Thickness				
Strength (MPa)	4.3	2.4	2.4	2.8
Modulus (GPa)	92	50	65	67

* Jaw slippage

Express in normalized graphs Figs. 5 and 6 depict the effects of hybrid level on the mechanical properties of the composites. It can be seen that the tensile strength and modulus are significantly improved as the proportion of SCS filament increases. This is to be expected as the SCS filament does not experience crimping and provides a good translation of fiber properties to the composite; in addition, the strength and modulus of the SCS filaments are superior to the Nicalon fibers . The local irregularities in the trends can be attributed to a limited set of data points, and, in the case of strength, insufficient data.

A reversed trend is observed for the through thickness strength and modulus as the proportion of axial fiber increases. The 100% braided structures demonstrates the highest through thickness properties because all of the yarns in the braided structure have some component oriented along the z axis relative to

yarn direction. Fig. 7 illustrates the fiber dominated failure mode of the composites. As the SCS-6 axial yarns are added to the system, the through-thickness strength decreases. Since the braiding yarn contributes significantly to the through-thickness direction, it is anticipated. A local increase in properties with SCS filament additions was unexpected. It is believed that, due to the distribution of bundles of SCS-6, the remaining Nicalon yarns are oriented more towards the through thickness direction, or z axis. The combination of higher z axis orientation balanced by reduced volume of fiber results in a reasonable trade-off of properties.

Flexural strength and modulus (Figures 5 and 6), on the other hand, show surprising results. It was expected that the flexural properties would follow a similar trend as in the case of simple tensile tests. By contrast, the results indicated an opposite trend. As the percentage of SCS-6 filament increases, the flexural strength decreases. No clear trend was observed in flexural modulus. It is believed that the placement of Avco filament within the braid is the dominant cause for this contradictory behavior. In general the SCS-6 filament is located in the interior of the composite, as shown in Fig.4b, thus experiencing a reduced compressive or tensile strain versus the Nicalon yarns. Combined with the increased out-of-plane orientation of the Nicalon fibers, the braiding yarns experience a high level of flexural strain in addition to the localized bending strain caused by yarn crimp. Thus, the Nicalon fibers on the tension side experiences fiber breakage whereas the Nicalon fibers on the compressive side tends to buckle. The fracture surfaces of the flexural specimens show fiber buckling on the specimens with a high proportion of SCS filaments and fiber breakage occurring on the specimens with low proportion of SCS filaments.

CONCLUSIONS

Hybrid SiC/LAS III composites were fabricated and tested in a 3-D braid architecture. Nicalon β -SiC was used as the braiding yarn and Avco SCS-6 as longitudinal lay-in. Nicalon was chosen for its fine diameter and ability to be processed into a textile structure. The SCS filament was chosen for its demonstrated high temperature resistance as well as excellent strength and modulus.

The preforms were consolidated with LAS III through slurry infiltration. Tensile flexural and through thickness tests were performed on the composites. The results of these tests indicate the potential for improved in-plane properties while maintaining a level of interlaminar strength, which is necessary for damage tolerance.

Flexural studies illustrate importance of geometric placement of the constituent fibrous materials particularly at the surface. The test results indicated, as the off-axis Nicalon fibers at the surfaces fail at a lower stress level, the localized bundles of the SCS filaments near the center of the braid do not contribute significantly to flexural strength. To maximize the potentials of this hybrid system, the SCS filaments should be distributed as uniformly as possible throughout the 3-D fiber network.

Through proper design and tailoring of the hybrid geometry, the combination of the Nicalon yarn and the SCS-6 filament presents a promising model material system for high temperature, structural applications.

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Figure 1. Four point Flexural Strength of SiC/LAS III Composites

Figure 2. Tensile Strength of Avco SCS-6 Monofilament After Thermal Exposure

Figure 3. Tensile Strength of Nicalon[®] SiC Yarn After Thermal Exposure

Figure 4a. Photomicrograph of 100% Nicalon SiC/LAS III Composite

Figure 4b. Photomicrograph of 50/50 Nicalon/Avco SiC/LAS III Composite

NORMALIZED PROPERTIES

Figure 5. Normalized Strength of Hybrid SiC/LASIII Composites

Figure 6. Normalized Modulus of Hybrid SiC/LASIII Composites

Figure 7. Through Thickness Fracture Surface of 100% Nicalon SiC/LASIII Composite